

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPUTATIONAL TOOL FOR THE STRUCTURAL DESIGN OF FOOTINGS

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ABSTRACT

The efficient and safe design of foundation elements is critical in structural engineering, requiring specialized computational support. To support this, several computational tools have been developed to facilitate project execution and organization. In structural design, for instance, it is often necessary to determine the dimensions of foundation elements. In this context, the present work proposes the development of a computational tool for the design of isolated footings, with a dual purpose: to serve as a didactic resource in undergraduate education and to assist designers who wish to carry out manual calculations. Developed entirely in Python, the tool's primary value lies in generating reliable results directly comparable to those found in established reference literature, thus facilitating validation. The program generates a comprehensive calculation report, which transparently presents a step-by-step application of the design equations, including all partial intermediate results at each stage, thereby improving the user's understanding of the underlying design methodology. An accompanying user manual was developed and presented for the tool. The program's substantial pedagogical value is demonstrated by its intuitive visual representation of the footing geometry, which consequently streamlines the definition and input of critical design parameters, such as column dimensions, axial load, bending moments, material resistance properties, and concrete cover.

KEYWORDS: *Isolated Footing, Foundation Design, Python, Sapcalc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Foundations are structural elements generally located below ground level, whose primary function is to receive, distribute, and transfer the loads from the superstructure to the supporting soil. This load transfer must occur in a manner that prevents differential settlements that could compromise the stability of the structure or induce soil failure [1]. Foundation design is a fundamental stage of building construction, as it encompasses the conception, sizing, and proper detailing of these elements. Its absence or inadequate execution may result in structural pathologies and high maintenance costs.

There are several types of foundations with distinct mechanical behaviors intended to efficiently accommodate the demands imposed by both the structure and the soil. According to ABNT NBR 6122 [2], foundations may be classified according to the depth of their bearing stratum as shallow (or surface) foundations and deep foundations.

The footing is a widely used type of shallow foundation, characterized as a reinforced concrete element capable of resisting tensile stresses through the reinforcement specifically arranged for this purpose [2]. Among the different types of footings, isolated footings are noteworthy due to their frequent application in small- to medium-scale projects and in situations where structural loads are concentrated at discrete

points, particularly due to their cost-effectiveness, ease of construction, and efficiency in soils with adequate bearing capacity [3].

Several studies have sought to develop computational tools for the design of foundations, especially isolated footings, using different programming languages and computational environments. Most of these tools are based on spreadsheet applications, employing Solver add-ins [4, 5], VBA routines [6, 7] or direct Excel implementations [8, 9]. Other studies explore different languages and platforms, such as software developed in Visual Basic [10, 11], scripts [12], Android applications in Java [13], software in C# [14], Smath Solver [15] and Python-based programs integrated with structural analysis tools [16]. In general, these solutions produce reliable and convergent results, with only minor discrepancies arising from rounding procedures and specific algorithmic characteristics [17, 18].

Although these tools contribute to the advancement of structural engineering, many are restricted to spreadsheets or proprietary software with limited accessibility, thereby constraining their practical use and updating according to current standards. Additionally, a considerable portion of the available computational tools for footing design is based on previous editions of the Brazilian standards ABNT NBR 6118 [19]. Given these constraints, the present work aims to develop a software application for the design of isolated footings, featuring a graphical user interface and entitled SapCalc, developed in Python 3.13 and grounded on the latest revisions of the relevant standards [2, 19]. This software functions as a practical and accessible tool to support both civil engineering professionals and students, presenting the step-by-step design procedures and corresponding results to facilitate data verification and comparison.

Following this introduction, the paper is structured into three main sections. Section 2, Design Principles of Isolated Footings, details the technical criteria adopted for the structural design, covering aspects such as construction details, dimensioning, eccentricity checks, internal bending moments, flexural reinforcement design, and additional verifications. Section 3, Methodology, describes the computational resources and development environment used, including the Python version, libraries employed, and the operational flowchart of the proposed software, SapCalc. Section 4, Results and Discussion, presents the user manual, a case study to validate the software against published literature, and a discussion of the results obtained. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions of the study.

II. DESIGN PRINCIPLES OF ISOLATED FOOTINGS

The software's design procedure is based on technical standards [2, 20, 21], which were implemented in this study. For the design, it is assumed that the centroid of the footing coincides with the centroid of the column [22]. The largest footing dimension (A) shall be limited to five times its smallest dimension (B). The column dimension (a_p), at the section corresponding to side A , and the footing height (h) are illustrated in the vertical section (Figure 1.a). The minimum footing dimension was set at 60 cm [2]. In the developed software, the overhangs c_A and c_B may be defined with equal values for an economical design, or with different values at the user's discretion (Figure 1.b).

Figure 1. Illustration of the dimensions of the isolated footing: (a) vertical section, (b) plan view.

The failure mechanism of a footing is similar to that of a flat slab, requiring checks for shear and punching. However, according to NBR 6118 [19], by simplifying the soil-structure interaction, footings can be classified as either rigid or flexible.

Rigid footings are subjected to bending in two directions, allowing tensile stresses to be assumed as uniformly distributed across the width, except for compression near the column or in very elongated footings. Shear also occurs in two directions, with failure governed by diagonal compression rather than diagonal tension. The uniform distribution of tensile stresses allows for continuous reinforcement placement and eliminates the need for punching verification, requiring only the analysis of diagonal compression [19].

Flexible footings exhibit non-uniform bending tension, concentrated near the column, and shear may be described by the punching phenomenon. Due to the small height of the footing, verification of punching, diagonal compression, and the stress distribution at the footing-soil interface is required [19].

Rigid footings are preferable to flexible ones because they are less susceptible to punching shear failure and therefore safer. Flexible footings are characterized by their small height. Compliance with the stiffness criterion is verified using Equation 1 [19].

$$h \geq \frac{A - a_p}{3} \quad (1)$$

Where: h is the footing height; A is the footing dimension in given direction and a_p column dimension in the same direction.

Due to the complexity of the analysis when considering non-uniform soil pressure, it is commonly assumed to be uniform under concentric loading, as the error introduced by this simplification is not significant [2, 19].

The design of isolated footings comprises the following steps: construction details, plan dimensions, determination of heights, determination of bending moments, design of bending reinforcement, reinforcement anchorage, punching verification.

2.1. Construction details

The footings designed by the software do not include a pedestal (collar), which corresponds to the dimensional offset between the top surface of the footing and the column face. To avoid potential edge failure of the footing, it is important that the external faces be executed vertically. The thickness h_0 at the footing edges shall comply with Equation 2 [23]:

$$h \geq \begin{cases} h/3 \\ 20 \text{ cm} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The inclination angle of the top surface of the footing shall be kept small ($\alpha \leq 30^\circ$) to avoid the use of formwork on these faces, reduce concrete consumption, and decrease the footing's dead load [23]. Figure 1(a) presents the construction details previously described.

2.2. Dimensions

Designers must select the plan dimensions of the footing to ensure that the bending moments in both directions result in approximately equal tensile forces in the reinforcement [20]. First, the base area of the footing is estimated using Equation 3. Then, the side lengths of the footing are determined using Equations (4) and (5) when the projections (cantilevers) are equal, or using Equations (6) and (7) when the projections are unequal. Figure 1(b) illustrates the adopted dimensions.

- Estimated base area of the footing:

$$S_{sap} = \frac{K_{maj} N_k}{P_{adm}} \quad (3)$$

- Footing dimensions for equal projections:

$$B = \frac{1}{2}(b_p - a_p) \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}(b_p - a_p)^2 + S_{sap}} \quad (4)$$

$$A = B - a_p - b_p \quad (5)$$

- Footing dimensions for unequal projections:

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{S_{sap}}{R}} \quad (6)$$

$$A = B \cdot R \quad (7)$$

- Footing projections:

$$c_A = \frac{A - a_p}{2} \text{ and } c_B = \frac{B - b_p}{2} \quad (8)$$

Where: S_{sap} is the estimated footing area; N_k : characteristic vertical load; K_{maj} : load increase factor; P_{adm} : allowable soil bearing pressure; B : shorter side of the footing; A : larger side of the footing; b_p : shorter side of the column; a_p : larger side of the column; R : aspect ratio of the footing, which must range between 1 and 3; c_A and c_B : projections in the directions of A and B , respectively.

The load increase factor (K_{maj}) accounts for the dead load of the footing and the overlying soil. It is recommended to either compute these loads or adopt an additional 5% to 10% of the permanent vertical load [20]. It is also noted that the side dimensions of the footing should preferably be multiples of 5 cm [22].

The total height of the footing (h) is defined according to the footing type, see Equation (1). The effective depth (d), given in Equation (9), must be sufficient to ensure the required anchorage length of the column starter bars ($l_{b,nec}$), calculated using Equations (10), (11) and (12)

- Effective depth of the footing:

$$d = h - (c + \phi) > l_{b,nec} \quad (9)$$

- Required anchorage length:

$$l_{b,nec} = 0.7 \cdot l_b \geq \begin{cases} 0.3 \cdot l_b \\ 10 \cdot \phi \\ 10 \text{ cm} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$l_b = \frac{\phi \cdot f_{yd}}{4 \cdot \eta_1 \cdot \eta_2 \cdot \eta_3 \cdot f_{ctd}} \geq 25 \cdot \phi \quad (11)$$

$$f_{ctd} = \frac{0.21 \cdot \sqrt[3]{f_{ck}^2}}{\gamma_c} \quad (12)$$

Where: d : effective depth; h : total footing height; c : concrete cover; ϕ : reinforcement bar diameter; $l_{b,nec}$: required anchorage length; l_b : basic anchorage length; f_{yd} : required anchorage length; η_1 , η_2 and η_3 : coefficients accounting for bar ribbing, bar position, and diameter, respectively; f_{ctd} : design tensile strength of concrete; f_{ck} : characteristic compressive strength of concrete; γ_c : partial safety factor for concrete.

2.3. Eccentricities

The allowable soil bearing pressure for footings subjected to eccentricities resulting from bending moments in one or both directions was determined according to a widely adopted methodology [24]. Several other Brazilian references present adaptations of this model in accordance with NBR 6118 [19, 20, 25].

2.4. Internal Bending Moments

For the CEB-70 method to be applied to rigid footings, the following geometric requirements must be satisfied, as expressed in Equation 13:

$$\frac{h}{2} \leq c_x \leq 2 \cdot h \quad (13)$$

Equation 13 must be satisfied for $c_X = c_A$ e para $c_X = c_B$. The method assumes that the distribution of soil reaction stresses over the footing–soil interface is linear. Horizontal forces are not considered in the calculation of the main flexural reinforcement.

The maximum bending moment in each direction of the footing is calculated at a planar reference section (S_{1A} ou S_{1B}), perpendicular to the support direction and located inside the column, specifically at a distance of 15% from the column face (Figure 4).

The effective depth (d) of the reference section is taken at the section parallel to S_1 and located at the column face, and must not exceed $1.5 c_x$. The bending moment related to the reference section S_1 is determined considering the soil reaction over the area between section S_1 and the nearest footing edge. The smaller bending moment acting on the footing, considering both directions, must be greater than or equal to one-fifth of the larger bending moment; that is, the ratio between the smaller and larger flexural reinforcement areas must exceed or equal $1/5$.

The bending moments acting at sections S_{1A} and S_{1B} , corresponding to the footing sides A and B , are determined by Equations (14)–(18):

- Bending moment at section S_{1A} :

$$M_{1A} = p \frac{x_A^2}{2} B \quad (14)$$

- Bending moment at section S_{1B} :

$$M_{1B} = p \frac{x_B^2}{2} A \quad (15)$$

- Soil pressure under the footing:

$$p = \frac{N_k}{A \cdot B} \quad (16)$$

- Distances from the reference sections to the footing edges:

$$x_A = c_A + 0.015 \cdot a_p \quad (17)$$

$$x_B = c_B + 0.015 \cdot b_p \quad (18)$$

It is not necessary to consider the dead load of the footing or the weight of the overlying soil for the calculation of p , since they do not induce bending in the footing.

The bending moments are calculated for both directions of the footing at the sections passing through its centroid. When the soil pressure at the base is non-uniform, a procedure is adopted to convert it into an equivalent uniform pressure. The software designs flexible footings using areas composed of

trapezoidal stress distributions, in which the bending moments and shear forces are computed according to Equations (19)–(22).

- Bending moment at the footing center in the A-side:

$$M_A = \frac{N}{4} \left[\left(\frac{A - a_p}{6} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{2B + b_p}{B + b_p} \right) + \frac{a_p}{6} \right] \quad (19)$$

- Bending moment at the footing center in the B-side:

$$M_B = \frac{N}{4} \left[\left(\frac{B - b_p}{6} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{2A + a_p}{A + a_p} \right) + \frac{b_p}{6} \right] \quad (20)$$

- Shear force in the A-side:

$$V_A = p \frac{N}{4} \left[\left(1 - \frac{b_p}{B} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{a_p}{A} \right) \right] \quad (21)$$

- Shear force in the B-side:

$$V_B = p \frac{N}{4} \left[\left(1 - \frac{b_p}{B} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{a_p}{A} \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

2.5. Flexural reinforcement

For footings with inclined upper surfaces, the compressed concrete section assumes a trapezoidal shape, which must be considered in the flexural reinforcement design [25]. As a simplified alternative, the flexural reinforcement may be calculated by assuming a rectangular section with a lever arm of $z = 0.85 \cdot d$, for which the resulting error does not exceed 10% (Equation (23)).

- Flexural reinforcement area:

$$A_s = \frac{M_d}{0.85 \cdot d \cdot f_{yd}} \quad (23)$$

To avoid potential issues during concrete casting, it is common practice to adopt a minimum reinforcement spacing (e). In this study, a minimum spacing of 10 cm is adopted for this parameter. It is also recommended that $e \leq 20$ cm [19]. The flexural reinforcement is uniformly distributed along the width of the footing, extending continuously from one edge to the opposite edge, and terminating with hooks at both ends.

2.5. Additional verifications to be performed for the design of footings

Other verifications performed in the design of isolated footings include punching shear, splitting, overturning, and sliding. Punching shear verification corresponds to checking shear on two or more critical surfaces around concentrated forces. Splitting verification is carried out in a horizontal plane for reinforcing bars with $\phi \geq 25$ mm. Splitting refers to the formation of cracks in the concrete footing, usually caused by tensile stresses that exceed the capacity of the reinforcement. Overturning occurs when the footing tends to rotate about its edge due to eccentric or asymmetrical actions, which may lead to loss of stability. Sliding refers to the horizontal displacement of the footing relative to the soil, caused by lateral forces that exceed the available frictional resistance.

The verification procedures for footings are established by Brazilian standards [2, 19]. For simplification purposes, the program performs the checks for punching shear, splitting, and overturning. The program does not verify sliding, as this requires soil information beyond the allowable bearing pressure.

III. METHODOLOGY

For the development of the proposed software, an approach was adopted that combines modern computational tools with established design standards. The following subsections describe the programming resources, libraries employed, development environment, compilation procedures, and technical design criteria, to present the methodology adopted for the implementation of the program.

The program was developed in Python (version 3.13.5), selected due to its ease of learning, readability, and versatility, particularly given the wide range of available support libraries. The graphical user interface was implemented using the Tkinter library, primarily through widgets from the ThemedTk module, while the math library was used for specific computational procedures. Complementary libraries include: os for interaction with the operating system; json for handling JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) files; sys for communication with the program's execution environment; and PIL (Python Imaging Library) for image processing.

For code organization and maintenance, the PyCharm 2025.1 Integrated Development Environment (IDE), developed by JetBrains, was employed. This IDE offers features such as coding assistance, code inspection, and file navigation, thereby streamlining programming efforts. After development, an executable file was generated using the PyInstaller tool, which converts Python scripts into standalone executables, enabling the use of the software on devices without a Python interpreter installed. This process resulted in the creation of the computational tool SapCalc, intended for the design of isolated footings.

The software was designed to comply with the requirements of Brazilian Standards [2, 19], ensuring the structural design of isolated footings able to withstand actions at the Ultimate Limit State (ULS). The methodology implemented adheres to recommendations provided in the technical literature for the design of isolated footings [23], as well as current Brazilian standards.

3.1. General structure of the system

The footing design procedure is illustrated in the flowchart shown in Figure 2. The grey boxes represent the steps performed by the user, while the white boxes correspond to the stages automatically executed by the software.

Figure 2. Flowchart of SapCalc's operation.

When launching the program, the user must first select the desired options in the Information section: type of footing and type of stiffness. In the Isolated Footing Information section, the following input data must be entered or selected: dimensions a_p and b_p (column cross-section dimensions); column rebar size; axial load N_k ; bending moments M_a and M_b ; type of concrete; type of steel; allowable bearing capacity; concrete cover; cantilevers; and aspect ratio A/B . If the user wishes to reopen a

previously saved file, they should select Open in the File menu and choose the desired file; this action automatically fills in the input fields.

Next, by clicking Next, the user will be prompted to save the input data to a file. If the file is not saved or if any required field is left blank, the program will not proceed to the next step. Once the file is saved, the software automatically performs the footing design.

The user may still modify the following parameters in the Parameters Used in the Calculations section: coefficient c (γ_c); coefficient f (γ_f); coefficient s (γ_s); coefficient k_{maj} (k_{maj}); flexural reinforcement bar diameter [mm] (for the footing); increase in footing thickness [cm]; and increase of the smaller footing side (B) [cm]. To apply the new parameter values to the design, the user must click Apply Changes, after which the program recalculates and updates the footing design.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. User Manual

The initial screen (Figure 3) is the first interface displayed when launching SapCalc. At the top, the menu bar contains the items “File”, “Edit”, and “Help”, which remain accessible at any time throughout the use of the software.

Below the menu bar, the main window is divided into two sections. The “Information” section displays the file name, the selected type of footing, and the stiffness type. The “Isolated Footing Data” section contains the input fields required for the footing design, organized into related groups for easier data entry.

Figure 3. SapCalc home screen.

A footing diagram is displayed on the screen to assist the user. The variables required for input are as follows: a_p and b_p – dimensions of the column cross-section; N_k – total vertical concentric load (characteristic axial force); M_a and M_b – bending moments acting about the directions corresponding to the a_p and b_p sides of the column, respectively.

The available units of measurement for data entry are: Lengths: meter [m], centimeter [cm], millimeter [mm]. Rebar diameter: centimeter [cm], millimeter [mm]. Axial load: newton [N], kilonewton [kN]. Bending moments: newton-meter [N·m], kilonewton-meter [kN·m], kilonewton-centimeter [kN·cm]. Allowable soil bearing capacity: megapascal [MPa], kilonewton per square centimeter [kN/cm²], kilogram-force per square centimeter [kgf/cm²].

It is recommended to avoid using negative values for bending moments. When entering the data, be aware that the decimal separator must be a period (“.”). The use of a comma for decimal separation is not supported. After filling in all fields, click the “Next” button to save the data and proceed with the design process.

The results screen (Figure 3) is only accessible after all input fields on the initial screen have been completed and the file containing this information has been saved to a directory. On this screen, the “Isolated Footing Data” section is replaced by “Isolated Footing Design”. This interface includes vertical and horizontal scroll bars and displays a step-by-step description of the design process.

Figure 4. SapCalc Output Results Screen.

Under the “Information” section, there is the “Parameters” section, which contains the subsections “Coefficients” and “Others”. Their purpose is to display the values used in the design and to allow the user to adjust them if desired. The data that may be modified in the “Parameters” section are:

Coefficients: Concrete partial safety factor (γ_c): weighting factor for concrete; Load partial safety factor (γ_f): weighting factor for actions; Steel partial safety factor (γ_s): weighting factor for reinforcing steel; k_{maj} factor: magnifying factor applied to the vertical load of permanent actions.

Others: Flexural reinforcement bar diameter [mm]: changes the bar diameter used in the footing reinforcement calculation; Increase height [cm]: adds the specified value to the basic footing height h , which may be required when increasing the final height; Increase smaller side (B) [cm]: adds the specified value to the smallest footing dimension B , consequently increasing the remaining dimensions of the footing base.

After modifying any value, the “Apply changes” button must be pressed to recalculate the isolated footing design. The “Next” button is disabled and the “Back” button is enabled, allowing the user to return to the initial screen.

The “File” menu contains the following items: New: returns to the initial screen with all input fields reset to default settings; Open: opens a dialog box allowing the user to select a JSON file from the file system; Save: saves the data currently entered in the input fields to the loaded file. Empty fields overwrite previously saved data, if any. If no file is loaded, it behaves as the next item; Save As...: opens a dialog box allowing the user to save a JSON file to the file system; Exit: closes the application.

The “Edit” menu contains the following items: Font: allows the user to select a font for the application; Theme: allows the user to select a theme for the application. The “Help” menu contains the following

item: About: information about SapCalc. All menus may be accessed at any time while the program is running.

4.2. Case Study

Two examples are presented to demonstrate the operation of SapCalc. The objective is to display the results generated by the software and compare them with the results obtained by the authors. Table 1 presents the input parameters required for the design of the isolated footing in Examples 1 [21] and 2 [1].

Table 1. Input data for examples 1 and 2.

	a_p (cm)	b_p (cm)	$\phi_{l,pil}$ (mm)	N_k (kN)	f_{ck} (MPa)	f_{yk} (MPa)	c (cm)	P_{adm} (MPa)	$M_{k,A}$ (kN.m)	$M_{k,B}$ (kN.m)
Example 1	100	20	20	1600	25	500	4	0.3	100	0
Example 2	60	40	20	1040	20	500	4.5	0.5	280	190

The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results for Examples 1 and 2.

Parameters		Example 1	SapCalc	Example 2	SapCalc
Base dimensions	A (cm)	300	300	220	220
	B (cm)	220	220	200	200
	c_A (cm)	100	100	80	80
	c_B (cm)	100	100	80	80
Foundation height	Tipo	Rigid	Rigid	Rigid	Rigid
	h (cm)	80	80	75	75
	d (cm)	75	75	70	69.5
	h_0 (cm)	30	30	35	25
	α_A	26.6°	26.5651°	30°	32.0054°
	α_B	26.6°	26.5651°	30°	32.0054°
Internal bending moments acting on the structure	σ_{max} (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	3.818	382	-	-
	σ_{min} (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	2.970	297	-	-
	σ_1 (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	-	-	591	591
	σ_4 (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	-	-	-591	-65
	σ_2 (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	-	-	317	309
	σ_3 (kN/cm ²) ^{a'}	-	-	215	217
	x_A (cm)	115	115	89	89
	x_B (cm)	103	103	86	86
	p_A (kN/cm ²)	3.716	371	- ^{b'}	450
	p_B (kN/cm ²)	3.394	340	- ^{b'}	404
	M_{IAd} (kN.cm)	54059	53970.38	32047 ^{c'}	49902.30
M_{IBd} (kN.cm)	54010	54105.90	29586 ^{c'}	46014.95	
Bending reinforcement	A_{sA} (cm ²)	19.50	19.4716	23.1	19.4287
	A_{sB} (cm ²)	19.49	19.5205	21.0	17.9152
Reinforcement detailing ^{d'}	Number of bars	A ^{d'} : 24 B ^{e'} : 24	A ^{d'} : 25 B ^{e'} : 25	A ^{d'} : 18 B ^{e'} : 17	A ^{d'} : 16 B ^{e'} : 15
	Diameter of bars (mm)	A ^{d'} : 10 B ^{e'} : 10	A ^{d'} : 10 B ^{e'} : 10	A ^{d'} : 12.5 B ^{e'} : 12.5	A ^{d'} : 12.5 B ^{e'} : 12.5
	Spacing between bars (cm)	A ^{d'} : 9 B ^{e'} : 12	A ^{d'} : 9 B ^{e'} : 12	A ^{d'} : 12 B ^{e'} : 12	A ^{d'} : 12 B ^{e'} : 14.5
	Length of bars (cm)	A ^{d'} : 372 B ^{e'} : 292	A ^{d'} : 368 B ^{e'} : 288	A ^{d'} : 240 B ^{e'} : 220	A ^{d'} : 321 B ^{e'} : 301

^a σ_{\max} and σ_{\min} are parameters from Example 1, while $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ e σ_4 are parameters from Example 2; ^b Values not available; ^c Calculation method different from that used in the study; ^d Values in direction A (Figure 1.b.); ^e Values in direction B.

Based on the results presented in Table 2, it can be observed that the values obtained using SapCalc and those extracted from the references are virtually identical, with differences arising only from rounding, slightly affecting subsequent results, or from assumptions adopted by the authors, such as the value of h_0 in Example 2.

The main discrepancy occurs in the internal bending moments of Example 2, resulting from the application of different equations for computing the bending moments in each direction, as well as for determining the required flexural reinforcement area. These variations become evident when compared with the data generated by SapCalc.

Nevertheless, such differences do not invalidate the results provided by SapCalc, since the detailing of footings, when compliant with Brazilian standards, may vary according to the designer's assumptions and adopted design criteria.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The development of this study resulted in a didactic computational tool for the design of isolated footings in accordance with the most recent editions of the Brazilian standards [2, 19]. A user manual was also developed. The tool has proven to be highly educational, as it presents visual illustrations of the footing geometry, which facilitates the input of parameters such as column dimensions, axial load, bending moments, concrete and steel strength, and concrete cover.

The results are presented in a clear and instructional manner. The footing dimensions, calculated based on the preliminary design, are also displayed graphically. In addition, the program provides a summarized calculation report, showing a step-by-step explanation of how the design equations are applied, and presenting partial intermediate results in each design stage, thereby transforming the design process into an effective pedagogical tool.

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